

Heavy Metal Contamination in Soil of Industrial Area, Dewas, Madhya Pradesh, India

Reeta Kori¹, Alok Saxena², Harish Wankhade³, Asad Baig⁴, Ankita Kulshreshtha^{5*}, Saket Mishra⁶, Smriti Sen⁷

Central Laboratory, Madhya Pradesh Pollution Control Board, Paryavaran Parisar, E-5, Arera Colony, Bhopal, India

Abstract—A study has been conducted to assess the heavy metal contamination in soil of Dewas industrial area of Madhya Pradesh, India. Total eight locations and one control location were selected in Dewas industrial area for soil quality monitoring w.r.t. heavy metals. The nine soil samples were monitored for heavy metals such as Chromium (Cr), Manganese (Mn), Nickel (Ni), Copper (Cu), Zinc (Zn), Iron (Fe), Cadmium (Cd), Lead (Pb) and Cobalt (Co) analysis during different four quarters from April 2019 to March 2020. The heavy metal contamination with w.r.t. Contamination Index (CI), Pollution Load Index (PLI) study in selected locations in Dewas industrial area has been done. Over all Pollution Load Index of soil was found greater than 1 which shows polluted soil w.r.t. heavy metals at all selected monitoring locations in Dewas industrial area of Madhya Pradesh, India during this study.

Keywords— Industrial Area, Soil, Heavy Metals, Contamination Index (CI), Pollution Load Index (PLI).

I. INTRODUCTION

Heavy metals and trace elements are also a matter of concern due to their non biodegradable nature and long biological half-lives [1]. Soil pollution due to heavy metals, such as cadmium, lead, chromium, copper, and iron is a problem of concern. Although heavy metals are naturally present in soil, contamination comes from local sources: mostly industry, agriculture, waste incineration, combustion of fossil fuels, and road traffic. The most important sources of heavy metals in soil are the anthropogenic activities such as mining, smelting procedures, steel & iron industry, chemical industry, traffic, and agriculture as well as domestic activities [2–11]. Soil is a dynamic medium made up of many minerals, organic matter, water, air, living creatures including bacteria and earthworms. It was formed by changing due to physical factors; the parent material, time, the climate and organisms present in composition. Generally polluted water also pollutes soil as it percolate in it. Solid waste is a mixture of plastics, cloth, glass, metal and organic matter, sewage, sewage sludge, building debris, generated from households, commercial and industries establishments add to soil pollution. Fly ash, iron & steel slag, medical & industrial wastes disposed on land are important sources of soil pollution. Chemical and metallurgical industries are the most important sources of heavy metals in soil [12–14]. The problem of soil pollution due to toxic metals has begun to cause concern now in most of the major cities. Soil pollution in the environment with toxic metals has increased dramatically since the onset of the industrial revolution [15-16]. Heavy metals in soil plays important role in biological system but it can cause harm if it in higher concentration in any system of environment. Therefore concentration of Contamination Index (CI), Pollution Load Index (PLI) w.r.t. heavy metals in Dewas Industrial area in Madhya Pradesh, India is important.

II. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Area

Dewas District in Ujjain Revenue Division, is situated on the Malwa plateau in the West-central part of Madhya Pradesh, India and lies between 20°17' and 23°20' North latitude and 75°54' and 77°08' East longitude. The district is bounded by Ujjain district in the north, Indore district in the west, West-Nimar district in the south-west, East Nimar district in the south, Hoshangabad district in the South East, Sehore district in the east and Shajapur district in the North-East.

2.2 Monitoring Locations

Dewas industrial area is consist of four industrial area i.e. Industrial Area 1, Industrial Area 2 & 3, Sia Industrial Area, Ujjain Road Industrial Area. Total eight locations and one control location in different industrial area in Dewas were selected for soil is depicted in table no 1 and figure no 1.

TABLE 1
MONITORING LOCATIONS AT DEWAS INDUSTRIAL AREA

S.N	Code	Industrial Area	Monitoring Locations	Latitude & Longitude
1.	S1	Industrial Area 1	Near M/S White star milk and milk products , Dewas	22.5754 & 76.2453
2.	S2	Industrial Area 1	Near M/S Tata International Ltd, Dewas	23.1064 & 77.52432
3.	S3	Industrial Area 1	Near M/S Raj Pioneer Laboratories (India), Dewas	23.07689 & 77.55652
4.	S4	Industrial Area 2 & 3	Near M/S Roca Bathroom Products Pvt Ltd (Parryware Industry) Dewas	23.11448 & 77.51583
5.	S5	Industrial Area 2 & 3	Near M/S VE Commercial Vehicle Ltd unit 2 (Eicher), Dewas	23.10886 & 77.51757
6.	S6	Industrial Area 2 & 3	Near M/S Navin Fluorine International Ltd, Dewas	23.09844 & 77.52922
7.	S7	Sia Industrial Area	Near M/S Krishna Food Products Ltd, Dewas	23.08073 & 77.53493
8.	S8	Ujjain Road Industrial Area	Near M/S Kriloskar Brother's Ltd, Dewas	23.07719 & 77.54176
9.	CS (Control Site)	Ujjain Road Industrial Area	Near M/S Bank Note Press , Dewas	23.07449 & 77.53204

FIGURE 1: Monitoring Locations at Dewas industrial area

2.3 Monitoring

All soil samples were collected as per standard guidelines followed by Central Pollution Control Board. The aliquots of soil mixed together (unwanted matters to be separated manually before mixing of samples) during collection from the each selected sampling area. Out of this mixture, approx. 500 gm sample to be taken into polypropylene zip pouch, duly coded,

labeled at field as per guidelines of Central Pollution Control Board. Soil samples were collected from the outer surface, i.e. 05–15 cm depth, after removing surface contamination. Sampling was carried out using a plastic spatula and the use of metal tools was avoided. The samples were collected in self-locking polythene bags and were sealed in double bags.

2.4 Digestion and Analysis:

Soil samples were dried for two days at room temperature. The dry soil sample was disaggregated with mortar and pestle. The sample was finely powdered to –250 mesh size (US Standard) using a swing grinding mill. All soil samples were digested by EPA Method 3050B (Acid Digestion of Sediments, Sludges and Soils) and analyzed by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer Pinnacle 900H) [17].

2.5 Soil Pollution Indices

Pollution assessment models are indicators used to assess the presence and intensity of anthropogenic contaminant deposition on soils. In this study, the following pollution assessment models were employed: Contamination Index (CI), Pollution Load Index (PLI) w.r.t heavy metals concentration present in soil.

2.5.1 Contamination Index (CI):

The contamination factors were derived by using the CI equation as defined [18]:

$$CF = C_n / B_n \quad (1)$$

Where C_n = measured metal concentration and B_n = background concentration from control site. The concentration factor observe as; $CF < 1$ low; $1 < CF < 3$ moderate; $3 < CF < 6$ considerable, and $CF > 6$ as high contamination [19].

2.5.2 Pollution Load Index (PLI):

The PLI gives a generalized assessment on the level of soil contamination. The PLI is obtained using approach as follows [20]:

$$PLI = [CF_1 \times CF_2 \times CF_3 \times \dots \times C_n]^{1/n} \quad (2)$$

Where, CF = contamination factor; and n = number of metals. $PLI > 1$ indicates pollution exists; $PLI < 1$ indicates no metal pollution [21]; and $PLI = 1$ indicates heavy metal loads close to the background level [22].

III. RESULT & DISCUSSION

The observed concentration of heavy metals in soil is depicted in Table 2. Contamination index (CI) and Pollution load index (PLI) w.r.t. heavy metals in soil of all selected locations are presented in Table 3. All results are shown in figure no. 2 to figure no 11.

TABLE 2
HEAVY METALS CONCENTRATION IN SOIL

S.N	Analytes	Unit	CS	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8
1	Cr	mg/kg	89	113	149	127	230	545	120	417	129
2	Mn	mg/kg	524	921	1301	927	771	1566	1105	891	1274
3	Ni	mg/kg	42	43	73	65	43	90	61	52	47
4	Cu	mg/kg	81	172	192	153	129	146	117	110	179
5	Zn	mg/kg	89	140	114	110	124	116	99	119	173
6	Co	mg/kg	30	36	42	38	34	39	38	32	42
7	Cd	mg/kg	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
8	Fe	mg/kg	15323	46456	56801	48573	33429	52437	43657	27668	45858
9	Pb	mg/kg	59	63	118	93	89	93	102	72	116

TABLE 3
CONTAMINATION INDEX (CI) AND POLLUTION LOAD INDEX (PLI) OF SOIL

Heavy Metal	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8
Cr	1.269	1.674	1.426	2.584	6.123	1.348	4.685	1.449
Mn	1.757	2.482	1.769	1.471	2.988	2.108	1.7	2.431
Ni	1.023	1.738	1.547	1.023	2.142	1.452	1.238	1.119
Cu	2.123	2.37	1.888	1.592	1.802	1.444	1.358	2.209
Zn	1.573	1.28	1.235	1.393	1.3	1.112	1.337	1.943
Co	1.2	1.4	1.266	1.133	1.3	1.266	1.066	1.4
Cd	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
Fe	3.031	3.706	3.169	2.181	3.422	2.849	1.805	2.992
Pb	1.067	2	1.576	1.508	1.576	1.728	1.22	1.966
Pollution Load Index (PLI)	1.573	1.827	1.568	1.47	2.051	1.633	1.636	1.869

Figure no 2 is showing that average concentration of Chromium (Cr) was found 89 mg/kg at control site (CS). Minimum average concentration was found 120 (S6) mg/kg and maximum average concentration was found 545 (S5) mg/kg during this study.

FIGURE 2: Chromium (Cr) concentration in Soil

Figure no 3 is showing that average concentration of Manganese (Mn) was found 524 mg/kg at control site (CS). Minimum average concentration was found 771 (S4) mg/kg and maximum average concentration was found 1566 (S5) mg/kg during this study.

FIGURE 3: Manganese (Mn) concentration in Soil

Figure no 4 is showing that average concentration of Nickel (Ni) was found 42 mg/kg at control site (CS). Minimum average concentration was found 43 (S1) mg/kg and maximum average concentration was found 90 (S5) mg/kg during this study.

FIGURE 4: Nickel (Ni) concentration in Soil

Figure no 5 is showing that average concentration of copper (Cu) was found 81 mg/kg at control site (CS). Minimum average concentration was found 110 (S7) mg/kg and maximum average concentration was found 192 (S2) mg/kg during this study.

FIGURE 5: Copper (Cu) concentration in Soil

Figure no 6 is showing that average concentration of zinc (Zn) was found 89 mg/kg at control site (CS). Minimum average concentration was found 99 (S6) mg/kg and maximum average concentration was found 173 (S8) mg/kg during this study.

FIGURE 6: Zinc (Zn) concentration in Soil

Figure no 7 is showing that average concentration of Cobalt (Co) was found 30 mg/kg at control site (CS). Minimum average concentration was found 32 (S7) mg/kg and maximum average concentration was found 42 (S2, S8) mg/kg during this study.

FIGURE 7: Cobalt (Co) concentration in Soil

Figure no 8 is showing that average concentration of cadmium (Cd) was found 1 mg/kg at control site (CS). Minimum average concentration was found 1 (S2, S3, S4, S5) mg/kg and maximum average concentration was found 2 (S1, S6, S7, S8) mg/kg during this study.

FIGURE 8: Cadmium (Cd) concentration in Soil

Figure no 9 is showing that average concentration of iron (Fe) was found 15323 mg/kg at control site (CS). Minimum average concentration was found 27668 (S7) mg/kg and maximum average concentration was found 56801 (S2) mg/kg during this study.

FIGURE 9: Iron (Fe) concentration in Soil

Figure no 10 is showing that average concentration of lead (Pb) was found 59 mg/kg at control site (CS). Minimum average concentration was found 63 (S1) mg/kg and maximum average concentration was found 118 (S2) mg/kg during this study.

FIGURE 10: Lead (Pb) concentration in Soil

Figure no 11 is showing that Pollution Load Index (PLI) was found 1.47 (S4) and maximum Pollution Load Index was found 2.051 (S5). Over all Pollution Load Index was found greater than 1 which shows polluted soil w.r.t. heavy metals at all selected monitoring locations during this study.

FIGURE 11: Pollution Load Index w.r.t. Heavy Metals in Soil

IV. CONCLUSION

Almost three fourths of the area in the Dewas district is covered by black cotton soils, which is occupied by Deccan Basalts. The southern part has red yellow mixed soils derived from sandstone, shale, gneiss. The heavy metal contamination with w.r.t. Contamination Index (CI), Pollution Load Index (PLI) study in selected locations in Dewas industrial area has been done. Over all Pollution Load Index of soil was found greater than 1 which shows polluted soil w.r.t. heavy metals at all selected monitoring locations in Dewas industrial area of Madhya Pradesh, India during this study.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the help received from authorities of monitoring locations of Dewas industrial area. We all authors acknowledge to the Chairman and Member Secretary, Madhya Pradesh Pollution Control Board, for encouragement of study work and kind permission to publish this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] Rahman S H, Khanam D, Adyel T M, Islam M S, Ahsan M A and Akbor M A. (2012) Assessment of Heavy Metal Contamination of Agricultural Soil around Dhaka Export Processing Zone (DEPZ), Bangladesh: Implication of Seasonal Variation and Indices. *Appl. Sci.* 2, 584-601.
- [2] Suciú C I, Cosma M, Todiciá S D, Bolboaciá and Jantschi L. (2008) Analysis of soil heavy metal pollution and pattern in central Transylvania. *Int J of Mole Sci.* 9, 434-453.
- [3] Chopin E I B and Alloway B J. (2007) Distribution and mobility of trace elements in soils and vegetation around the mining and smelting areas of Tharsis, Riotinto and Huelva, Iberian Pyrite Belt, SW Spain. *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution.* 182, 1-4, 245-261.
- [4] Garcia R and Millán E. (1998). Assessment of Cd, Pb and Zn contamination in roadside soils and grasses from Gipuzkoa (Spain). *Chemosphere.* 37, 8, 1615-1625.
- [5] Li X, Poon C S, and Liu P S. (2001) Heavy metal contamination of urban soils and street dusts in Hong Kong. *Applied Geochemistry.* 16, 11-12, 1361-1368.
- [6] Sezgin N, Ozcan H K, Demir G, Nemlioglu S, and Bayat C. (2004) Determination of heavy metal concentrations in street dusts in Istanbul E-5 highway. *Environment International,* 29, 7, 979-985.
- [7] Viard B, Pihan F, Promeyrat S, and Pihan J C. (2004) Integrated assessment of heavy metal (Pb, Zn, Cd) highway pollution: bioaccumulation in soil, graminaceae and land snails. *Chemosphere.* 55, 10, 1349-1359.
- [8] Nabulo G, Oryem-Origa H, and Diamond M. (2006) Assessment of lead, cadmium, and zinc contamination of roadside soils, surface films, and vegetables in Kampala City, Uganda. *Environmental Research.* 101, 42-52, 2006.
- [9] Oliva S R and Espinosa A J F. (2007) Monitoring of heavy metals in topsoils, atmospheric particles and plant leaves to identify possible contamination sources. *Microchemical Journal.* 86,1; 131-139.
- [10] Kampa M and Castanas E. (2008) Human health effects of air pollution. *Environmental Pollution.* 151, 2, 362-367.
- [11] Guo-li L, Da-xue, L and Quan-ming L. (2008) Heavy metals contamination characteristics in soil of different mining activity zone Trans, *Transactions of Nonferrous Metals Society of China.* 18, 1, 207-211.
- [12] Pantelica A, Cercasov V, Steinnes E, Bode P and Wolterbeek B. (2008) in *Proceedings of the 4th National Conference of Applied Physics (NCAP '08)*, 25-26, Galati, Romania, September.
- [13] De Vries W, Romkens P F and Schütze G (2007). Critical soil concentrations of cadmium, lead, and mercury in view of health effects on humans and animals. *Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology.* 191, 91-130.
- [14] Cojocarú V, Panteliciá A, Pincovschi E and Georgescu I. (2006) EDXRF versus INAA in a pollution control of soil. *Journal of Radioanalytical and Nuclear Chemistry.* 268, 1, 71-78.
- [15] Bangalore Metropolitan Rapid Transport Limited, *Environmental Impact Analysis*, 2006.
- [16] Nriagu J O (1979) "Global inventory of natural and anthropogenic emissions of trace metals to the atmosphere. *Nature,* 279, 409-411.
- [17] *Acid Digestion of Sediments, Sludges and Soils, EPA Method 3050B, Revision 2 December 1996.*
- [18] Lacutusu R. Appraising levels of soil contamination and pollution with heavy metals In Heinike HJ, Eckselman W, Thomasson AJ, et al. (2000). *Land information systems for planning the sustainable use of land resources. European Soil Bureau Research Report No. 4. Office of Official Publication of the European Communities, Luxembourg.* 393-402.
- [19] Hakanson L. (1980) An ecological risk index for aquatic pollution control: a sedimentological approach. *Water Res.* 14:975-1001.
- [20] Thomilson DC, Wilson DJ, Harris CR, et al. (1980). Problem in heavy metals in estuaries and the formation of pollution index. *Helgol Mar Res.* 33: 566-575.
- [21] Chakravarty M and Patgiri AD (2009). Metal pollution assessment in sediments of the Dikrong river, N.E. India. *J Hum Ecol.* 27(1):63-67.
- [22] Cabrera F, Clemente L and Barrientos DE. (1999). Heavy metal pollution of soils affected by the Guadamar toxic flood. *Sci Total Environ.* 242(1-3):117-129.